

Adoption of Integrated Reporting Practices in Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

Integrated Reporting (IR) has gained prominence as a mechanism to provide balanced information to stakeholders regarding value creation. This study aims to investigate the perceptions of IR within Sri Lankan companies. Primary data were gathered from accounting experts including corporate report preparers, auditors, investors/analysts, and other relevant stakeholders through an online questionnaire. The questionnaire comprised two sections: Section A focused on demographic factors, while Section B delved into IR adoption-related factors. Statistical analysis, utilizing the latest version of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), was employed to analyze the collected data. Descriptive analysis was conducted to interpret the findings. The study reveals a significant level of knowledge and awareness regarding IR among respondents. Integrated thinking promotion emerged as the primary perceived benefit, while the costs associated with IR preparation were identified as the main challenge. The study underscores the necessity for proper training seminars and workshops on formulating integrated reports, along with a reasonable timeframe for IR implementation, as recommended by respondents.

Keywords: Accounting Experts, Integrated Reporting, Perception, Sri Lanka

INTRODUCTION

Sudden company bankruptcies and financial crises have had an influence on global business success. As a result, the corporate environment has changed dramatically, and information transmission via social media and internet networks has grown increasingly sophisticated. Therefore, the provision of such information can be done through IR (Bananuka et al., 2019). The emergence of IR is due to the lack of information linkages in the current reporting system (Chaidali & Jones, 2017). IR is a novel and unique solution to existing corporate reporting practice that is now extensively employed in many nations using the International Integrated Reporting Framework - IIRF (Ahmed Haji & Anifowose, 2016). In some jurisdictions, IR is still not used by businesses, regulators, and especially governments in developing countries (Bananuka et al., 2019). International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) 2013, points out that IR helps to identify the sources of value creation. IR can be termed as a recently adopted model for combining various aspects of non-financial information into a “single report” (Romolini et al., 2017).

The Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) serves to meet the information needs of long-term investors, incorporate environmental and social factors into reporting, shift performance metrics towards medium to long-term outcomes, and align reporting with management's information needs. Emerging in response to the global financial crisis, Integrated Reporting (IR) is gaining traction worldwide. In Sri Lanka, both the Institute of Certified Management Accountants (ICMA) and the Institute of Chartered Accountants (ICASL) endorse its effective use. Similarly, countries like Australia are amending corporate governance codes to facilitate IR adoption, reflecting a significant global push towards its implementation.

IR is a new financial reporting system in Sri Lanka and currently, every company has to adopt and prepare this (Vickneswaran, 2019). At the time of the study Chaidali & Jones 2017, IR was under development. IR is still an immature concept in Sri Lanka. IR is very important to disclose physical information to the stakeholders for their sustainability.

Research Problem

Integrated Reporting (IR) represents a novel and progressive method in contemporary corporate reporting, gaining widespread adoption in numerous nations, as advocated by the

International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) proposed by Ahmed Haji and Anifowose in 2016. However, despite its proven benefits and acceptance in various regions, there remains a notable absence of integrated reporting adoption among businesses, regulatory bodies, and particularly governmental entities in developing nations (Bananuka et al., 2019). IR improves the quality of corporate reporting (CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, 2018). IIRC 2013 points out that IR helps to identify the sources of value creation.

The implementation of Integrated Reporting (IR) offers numerous advantages, yet it also presents several hurdles to adoption, both globally and within specific countries such as Sri Lanka. Extensive research endeavors conducted by diverse scholars across various nations have sought to discern the attitudes and perspectives regarding IR. To know the level of knowledge about IR in the respective country, to identify the benefits and challenges of IR in that country, to identify the form of IR in that country, and to identify the measures that can be taken to further develop IR by few people from few countries such as Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia test have been done.

IR adoption in Sri Lanka is at the nascent level. For IR to further develop in Sri Lanka, the perceptions of IR within Sri Lankan companies need to be identified. For that, this study was conducted to find out the perceptions of IR in Sri Lanka based on the Indonesian survey.

Many countries around the world are adopting IR. But in the Sri Lankan context, very few companies are preparing integrated reports. According to previous research, many companies are not preparing integrated reports. Therefore, this study is going to investigate what are the perceptions about IR in Sri Lankan companies. I mentioned the above objective as the main objective of this study. Likewise, other objectives can be demonstrated as follows.

- To identify the current level of knowledge about IR in Sri Lanka.
- To identify the major perceived benefits of IR adoption in Sri Lanka.
- To identify the major perceived challenges of IR adoption in Sri Lanka.
- To identify the form of IR adoption in Sri Lanka.
- To identify the support that can be needed for the widespread adoption of IR in Sri Lanka.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integrated Reporting

Sudden corporate collapses and financial crises have impacted business performance worldwide. Due to this, there has been a huge change in the business environment, and

communication of information through social media and internet networks has also become complicated. Therefore, the provision of such information can be done through IR (Bananuka et al., 2019). Apart from global competition, advancements in technology, and heightened regulatory demands, the aftermath of the global financial crisis, the absence of forward-looking insights, and the inadequate recognition of intangible assets have collectively instigated significant shifts in the business landscape. These challenges are potentially addressed by IR (CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, 2018). The emergence of IR is due to the lack of information linkages in the current reporting system (Chaidali & Jones, 2017).

Compared to traditional corporate financial reporting which was introduced in practice in the early 2000s, the IIRC established in 2010 has promoted IR (CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, 2018). IR is a new and innovative approach to current corporate reporting practice that is now widely used in many countries following the IIRF (Ahmed Haji & Anifowose, 2016). In some jurisdictions, IR is still not used by businesses, regulators, and especially governments in developing countries (Bananuka et al., 2019). IR improves the quality of corporate reporting (CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, 2018). IIRC 2013 points out that IR helps to identify the sources of value creation.

The current reporting duties are differentiated by their length, complexity, and statutory requirements. Furthermore, they often fail to adequately address emerging value drivers and the evolving business landscape, thereby prompting the adoption of Integrated Reporting (S. Adams & Simnett, 2011). The first experience of integrating financial and non-financial information began in 2002 with the production of the first IR by Novozymes. At the same time, other European and American companies also adopted IR (Sierra-García et al., 2015). Recently, many companies around the world have adopted the concept of IR, which goes beyond sustainability reporting in their financial. IR can be termed as a recently adopted model for combining various aspects of non-financial information into a “single report” (Romolini et al., 2017).

The process of Integrated Reporting (IR) hinges on integrated thinking, leading to the production of comprehensive reports by organizations, highlighting value creation over time and communicating various aspects of value creation effectively (IIRC 2013). The IR process is lengthy and requires a dedicated and skilled workforce (Bananuka et al., 2019). The Integrated Reporting Framework (IRF) describes the basic concepts of IR and establishes

guidelines for preparing integrated reports and identifies the content that should identify content that should be included (IIRC 2013).

Capital is transformed to create and preserve value for its beneficiaries (Albertini, 2019). According to IIRC 2013, IR represents six types of capital: financial, manufactured, intellectual, human, social and relational, and natural. IR takes a methodical approach to an organization's short-, medium-, and long-term operations (S. Adams & Simnett, 2011). According to the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) in 2011, the primary goal of an integrated report is to demonstrate how economic, social, environmental, governance, and financial aspects interact and influence a company's long-term performance. IR is growing popularity internationally (Kılıç & Kuzey, 2018). IR has become popular globally because of its ability to change the mindset of corporate decision-makers. It, therefore, strengthens the impact on decision-making and performance measurement systems (C. A. Adams, 2015).

Perception of IR

The perception of Integrated Reporting (IR) is impacted by both its positive consequences, such as opportunities and incentives, and its negative aspects, such as barriers and obstructions. This comprehensive evaluation influences stakeholders' views on the adoption and implementation of IR practices. Steyn (2014) utilizes a questionnaire survey to study the corporate advantages and implementation issues of required IR, with an emphasis on senior executives' perspectives in South African listed businesses. The average benefits of IR implementation are greater than the average challenges of IR implementation (Sugiarto, Estralita, Djeni 2021).

Some scholars have noted how the importance of IR has grown rapidly because of its many advantages (Frias-Aceituno et al., 2013). IR can provide internal benefits to an organization (S. Adams & Simnett, 2011). Transparency, insight into the future, and strategic directions of an organization are the benefits of IR to internal and external stakeholders (S. Adams & Simnett, 2011). The IIRC claims that investors and reporting organizations will benefit from adopting IR concerning the beneficiaries of IR. IR has the potential to reduce the burden of the annual report production process, break down the silos of traditional reporting and reduce the cost of the reporting process (Adams & Simnett, 2011). IR supports high-quality reporting, attracting foreign investors and capital inflows to the region. It indirectly affects economic and social

well-being (CASA FRANCA LOAYZA, 2018). The Institute of Accountants can encourage its members about IR and distribute information about the benefits of IR and how to prepare them (Bananuka et al., 2019).

Although IR has provided real opportunities for all organizations, its implementation has been hampered by certain barriers (Adams & Simnett, 2011). IR presents new challenges to existing auditing and assurance processes. In IR, the cost of systematically developing metrics and reporting on an integrated basis is huge for some organizations (Adams & Simnett, 2011). According to Adams & Simnett, 2011, the information required to produce an integrated report has been a stumbling block for many organizations. IR adoption can also affect social and environmental issues.

IR in the World

IR is a new reporting method and due to that, the studies conducted on IR are growing day by day. Due to this, various researchers have conducted studies on IR practices in different countries (Kılıç & Kuzey, 2018). The pace of IR adoption around the world is accelerating and over 1000 companies worldwide have implemented IR (IIRC 2016).

Ahmed Haji & Anifowose, 2016 studied IR practices in South Africa. For this, 82 companies preparing integrated reports in South Africa were selected and the integrated reports of those companies were obtained from sample websites. Despite variations in Integrated Reporting (IR) practices, there has been a discernible trend of ongoing enhancement among companies that have adopted IR. Researchers have concluded that contemporary employment of IR is often aimed at bolstering organizational legitimacy.

In their study Bananuka et al., 2019 investigated the implementation of Integrated Reporting (IR) in Uganda. Employing a narrative cross-sectional survey and qualitative data collection techniques, they also conducted an analysis of annual reports from listed companies. Their findings revealed several factors contributing to the sluggish uptake of IR in Uganda, including limited resources, cultural and leadership dynamics, stakeholder demands, regulatory constraints, global influences, low awareness of IR, and variations in business nature and scale. At the time of the study Chaidali & Jones (2017), IR was under development in the UK. Evidence is obtained through extensive interviews with corporate managers and planning

consultants on the perception of the integrated reports. According to the study done by Chaidali & Jones (2017), they pointed out that almost nothing is known about the practical adoption of IR. Many managers and planning consultants lack confidence in IR and preparers' opinion regarding the benefits of IR is the ability to improve performance. And also, they found it difficult to identify the beneficiaries of adopting IR. As an insight into the nature and implementation of IR can be gained from the perspectives of the preparers of integrated reports.

Hosoda (2020) conducted study on IR in Japan, collecting data through semi-structured interviews and emails shared with IR managers at seven Japanese organizations. They discovered the significance and necessity of incorporating integrated thinking into organizations at all levels. A study by Nicolò et al., 2020 found moderate levels of IR practices among European state-owned enterprises. According to the study done by Kılıç & Kuzey, 2018 they found that companies in Turkey are in the initial stage of IR adoption.

The study done by Hassan et al., 2019 based on 405 UK Higher Education Institutions found an increase in IR elements in annual reports over two years. A study by Nakib & Dey, 2018 based on listed companies preparing integrated reports in Bangladesh also found an improvement in IR practices in Bangladesh. A study by Ghosh, 2019 based on annual reports of 102 Indian companies has shown an improvement in IR practices in India. Eccles et al., 2015, although IR is a regulatory requirement in South Africa, it is voluntary in many countries around the world.

CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018) investigated IR in Indonesia. They collected data through surveys of authors contacted by the Indonesian Institute of Accountants (IAI), participants in general and executive training sessions, the Centre of Accounting Development, Universities Indonesia, and academics from other universities. And they discovered that, despite poor knowledge of IR, there is a strong interest in it. Because of the low level of knowledge about IR, it requires integrated training. For that, IR can be included in the university curriculum, and training, seminars, and conferences can be used. And also, they found that although there is a positive idea about the benefits of IR, reluctant to implement it.

The survey done by *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016 using a questionnaire found that the knowledge of IR in Malaysia was relatively slow. ISCA & NUS

2014, was conducted to understand the perception of IR in Singapore. It was found that there is still a low level of knowledge about IR in Singapore.

IR in Sri Lanka

IR is a new financial reporting system in Sri Lanka and currently, every company has to adopt and prepare this. In particular, publicly listed companies should adopt and prepare IR in Sri Lanka (Vickneswaran, 2019). Many Sri Lankan companies have adopted IR. Although it is a voluntary practice, the number of users of IR is increasing (N. Gunarathne & Senaratne, 2017). As of 2014, 32 companies in Sri Lanka have implemented IR, and the country was ranked as one of the world's fastest-growing (Gunarathne & Senaratne, 2017). In 2015, 32 companies in Sri Lanka implemented IR, which had grown to 85 by 2018 (Herath et al., 2019).

According to Gunarathne and Senaratne (2018), the high rate of IR adoption in Sri Lanka is due to variables such as a sufficient number of professional accountants, significant stakeholder demand, supportive accounting professions, fierce rivalry among firms, and cultural support. Vickneswaran (2019) stated that IR is still an immature concept in Sri Lanka. Although IR was earlier an efficient choice in Sri Lanka, it has now become a fashion choice (Gunarathne & Senaratne, 2018).

As in any other country, there are both benefits and challenges in adopting IR in Sri Lanka. Every company in Sri Lanka has more benefits from the adoption of IR (Vickneswaran, 2019). Some companies in Sri Lanka tend to adopt IR because of its benefits. Vickneswaran, (2019) found that the lack of awareness and knowledge regarding IR is the major limitation of the implementation of IR in Sri Lanka.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The analysis will be based on six indicators; awareness, perceived benefits, perceived challenges, primary recipients and preparers, standard and implementation and support, promotion, and training. This research primarily relies on original data from accounting specialists in Sri Lanka. The researcher then utilized the questionnaire to obtain information from accounting specialists.

In this study primary data was collected through a questionnaire developed by CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, 2018. The questionnaire comprises two distinct sections: Section A focuses on demographic factors, while Section B delves into IR adoption-related factors. In Section A, participants were asked to provide personal information without disclosing their names, a practice aimed at fostering sincerity and candor in their responses. This section included data points such as profession, age, gender, educational attainment, affiliation with professional accounting bodies, market competitiveness, company size, and years of work experience. Section B of the questionnaire on IR adoption-related factors by consisting twenty-two (22) questions. There are questions under each source or dimension of IR such as awareness of IR, perceived benefits of IR, perceived challenges of IR, primary recipients and preparers of IR, standards, implementation, support, promotion, and training. A sample of 102 accounting experts has been selected and those 102 accounting experts are working in Sri Lankan companies. For this study, the researcher used the deductive approach. This study is conducted to investigate what are the perceptions about IR in Sri Lankan companies. Furthermore, because the data for this study was collected across time, it may be classified as a cross-sectional study. Accounting specialists from Sri Lankan enterprises served as the study's unit of analysis. The researcher conducted descriptive analysis in this study using the most recent SPSS version 26.0.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Rate of Respondents

The researcher executed the questionnaire among 500 accounting experts of Sri Lankan companies. However, the researcher could only get answers from 102 out of 500 respondents.

The target population of the researcher is 500 accounting experts from Sri Lankan companies. But 102 of them responded to the questionnaire.

Demographic Data Analysis

This survey generated a total of 102 valid responses. The majority of the respondents (69.6%) are corporate preparers including CEOs, CFOs, financial controllers, and accountants of companies. Auditors and others including consultants, the staff of a regulatory body, and civil servants of companies form the next greatest number of respondents, comprising 22.5% and 4.9% respectively. The least number of respondents (2.9%) are investors/analysts. The majority of the respondents (44.1%) belong to the age group of 35-50 years while the rest are between 25-35 years of age (38.2%) and above 50 years of age (14.7%). People below the age of 25 years showed the lowest response rate (2.9%). Out of the total 102 respondents, 75.5% are male, and the remaining 24.5% are female.

When it comes to educational level, 69.6% of the total respondents are people with professional qualifications. Then people with a degree and postgraduate people responded at 16.7% and 13.7% respectively. None of the respondents chose the secondary school and others as their educational level. Most respondents (53.9%) are members of the ICASL. Of the remaining respondents, 15.7% are members of the CIMA and 11.8% are members of the ICMA. Then the ACCA (8.8%), Association of Accounting Technicians of Sri Lanka (7.8%), and IIA (2.0%) members responded respectively.

The majority of the respondents (51.0%) operate with high market competition. In the same way, the other respondents (40.2%) deal with moderate market competition, and the rest (8.8%) a low market competition. Most respondents (32.4%) said that their company size is above 10000M. 26.5% of the respondents indicated below 500M as the size of their company. Next, respectively 15.7% between 1000M-5000M, 13.7% between 500M-1000M and 11.8% between 5000M-10000M responded as their company size.

Considering the work experience of the 102 respondents, most people (35.3%) have experienced between 10-20 years. An equal percentage (25.5%) of the respondents stated that they have experienced between 5-10 years and above 20 years. The least number of respondents, i.e. 13.7% have less than 5 years of work experience.

Awareness of IR

4 Level of Knowledge of IR

According to the results of this study, Sri Lanka presently has enough understanding about Integrated Reporting. The researcher asked survey participants to rate their degree of knowledge on a scale of one (no knowledge) to five (excellent knowledge). Out of 102 respondents, 62.7% have adequate knowledge of IR and 24.5% have basic knowledge about IR. An equal number (5.9%) responded that they had minimal knowledge and superior knowledge of IR. The lowest percentage of 1.0% stated that they do not know IR in Sri Lanka.

IR is a relatively young initiative globally and adoptions by Sri Lankan companies have so far increased quite a bit. The above findings provide evidence that there is a fairly medium level of awareness of IR in Sri Lanka. The majority of these respondents have working knowledge or understanding of IR. Although this survey generally found intermediate levels of IR knowledge, survey participants were interested in learning more. The findings suggest that knowledge about IR can be further developed by further educating market participants about what IR is.

In a study conducted by CASA FRANCA LOAYZA (2018), it was found that as few as 19% of them had good or in-depth knowledge of IR. *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016 found that a very low percentage (13%) had good or in-depth knowledge about IR in that country. In ISCA & NUS 2014, 66.7% have no or low knowledge about it. All the surveys they have done about IR in Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore show that there is a very low level of knowledge about IR in those three countries. Compared with those three countries, there is adequate knowledge about IR in Sri Lanka.

Interested in Learn More about IR

Despite having adequate knowledge about IR in this study, the majority of the respondents (87.3%) stated that they are interested in learning more about IR / have an idea to learn more about IR. Meanwhile, 7.8% of the remaining people said that they have no idea to know more about IR. The remaining 4.9% said they were not sure about knowing more about IR.

According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), a higher percentage of people have an idea to know more about IR in the country. In the *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016, the majority of the people in that country are more interested in knowing more about IR. In Indonesia and Malaysia, the level of knowledge about IR is very low, so they are more interested in learning more about it. Although there is adequate knowledge about IR in Sri Lanka, they have an idea to learn more about it.

Deliberation of the Company's Board Level about IR

Accounting specialists who replied to this study reported that a bigger majority of them (62.7%) believe IR is considered by the company's board of directors, while another 6.9% are unsure. Only 30.4% rule out it. In another word, the IR of any of these companies has not been deliberated at the board level.

The ISCA & NUS, 2014, found that a low percentage of 15.6% said that they had discussed IR at the board level. The remaining 84.4% said that the company's board level does not deliberate on IR. In the *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016, it is clear that 31.3% responded that IR is discussed at the board level. Considering the survey conducted in Sri Lanka, it appears that more than Singapore and Malaysia responded that "IR is discussed at the company's board level.

Encouraging greater awareness and discussion of IR at the board level is important to encourage its wider adoption in the future. Likewise, board-level support for IR is especially important once organizations start adopting new initiatives such as IR. The involvement of board members is critical to ensure that new initiatives are properly embedded in management practices.

A Company's Consideration of Adopting IR

Among the respondents, a higher percentage (66.7%) indicated that their company would consider adopting IR while the remaining 20.6% ruled it out. Only 12.7% indicated that it was not sure. According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), as few as 31% said they would consider adopting IR. In the *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016, as few as 27.7% said that they are considering adopting IR. In the ISCA & NUS, 2014, a higher

percentage of 71.4% said they would consider adopting IR. In Indonesia and Malaysia, very few people contemplate IR adoption, whereas Singapore, like Sri Lanka, has a greater rate.

Active Supporter of IR

Out of the 102 respondents, most (83.3%) identified themselves as active supporters of IR. 10.8% indicated that they are not active supporters of IR. Likewise, a low percentage of 5.9% indicated that they had no idea about it. In the *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016, 32.5% of people said that they are active supporters of IR. According to the survey conducted in Sri Lanka, it is clear that more people are considered active supporters of IR than in Malaysia.

IR and Sustainability Reporting

A review of previous studies makes it clear that there is often confusion about whether there is any difference between IR and sustainability reports. Therefore, I directed that question to the participants of the survey. The majority of respondents (58.60%) see sustainability reporting as a subset of IR and 18.70% of people say that as not a perfect substitute but overlapped. Only a small percentage of respondents perceive sustainability reporting and IR as perfect substitutes (3.20%), or sustainability reporting is sufficient without IR (4.80%). 4.10% of people said that IR makes sustainability reporting redundant. And also 9.40% said that they haven't any idea about IR and sustainability reporting.

In the ISCA & NUS, 2014, a higher percentage of respondents (52.6%) indicated that sustainability reporting is a subset of IR. Only 26.7% of the respondents in Singapore got it right. That is, they say that there are no perfect substitutes but overlap. In the *MIA-ACCA Integrated Reporting Survey Contents*, 2016, a higher percentage of respondents (40.9%) indicated that sustainability reporting is a subset of IR. Only 12.4% of the respondents in Malaysia showed correct understanding. That is, they say that there are no perfect substitutes but overlap. Similar results are seen in Sri Lanka as in Singapore and Malaysia. In other words, more people in Sri Lanka have indicated that sustainability reporting is a subset of IR.

Perceived Benefits of IR

Received: 22 January 2024

Revised: 2 February 2024

Final Accepted: 11 February 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10647307>

72.5% of survey respondents said that the present corporate reporting system enabled them to effectively convey their company's worth and potential to produce value for investors and other stakeholders. 15.7% responded that the present corporate reporting system prevents them from effectively communicating their company's worth and capacity to produce value for investors and other stakeholders. The remaining 11.8% are doubtful if the present corporate reporting system enables them to effectively communicate their company's worth and potential to generate value for investors and other stakeholders. In the survey conducted by CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, (2018) on the above point, it was also revealed that a higher percentage (63%) agreed with that statement.

Among the respondents, 74.5% indicated that they could access satisfactory information regarding the company's value and its capacity to generate value from existing corporate reports. Conversely, 15.7% of the participants expressed difficulty in obtaining adequate information on the company's value and its capability to create value through the current corporate reporting mechanisms. The remaining 9.8% said they had not sure about it. A high percentage (65%) of the respondents in the CASAFRANCA LOAYZA, (2018) survey on this stated that current corporate reports provide sufficient information about the company's value and ability to create value.

The widespread use of IR by companies helps meet the information needs of investors and users. The majority of respondents (92.2%) stated that the use of IR helps to improve the quality of corporate reporting. 2.9% of the respondents said that the use of IR does not help to improve the quality of corporate reporting. The remaining 4.9% said that it is not sure whether the use of IR helps to improve the quality of corporate reporting. According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), its corporate report preparers (60%) said that IR helps to improve the quality of corporate reporting. Most of their respondents stated that.

According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA's 2018 results, the key benefits of implementing Integrated Reporting (IR) as identified by respondents internationally were developing integrated thinking, improving communication with external stakeholders, and increasing transparency and governance reporting. Similarly, respondents in Sri Lanka agreed that the most significant benefits were developing integrated thinking (58.8%), boosting communication with external stakeholders (56%), and improving transparency and governance reporting (33.8%). Furthermore, CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018) found that better access to money, higher share prices, and lower capital costs were viewed as less important benefits, which was shared by respondents in Sri Lanka. They shared similar opinions, putting improved access to finance (20.3%), higher share prices (14.3%), and lower capital expenses (11.8%) as very minor benefits of implementing IR.

Motivations for IR Adoption

When considering motivations for IR adoption, 53.9% of respondents indicated that the stakeholders' and other stakeholders' satisfaction is the most popular motivation method. As the second most popular method, 17.6% indicated that they would be motivated to adopt IR after learning that their competitors or similar companies prepare integrated reports. 12.7% of respondents said that the mandated corporate regulations are another motivation method for IR adoption. Being mandated by the accounting profession, as well as other approaches (to improve the quality of financial information, demonstrate the value of leveraging diverse resources, boost transparency, and produce reports more promptly), are additional motivators for implementing IR. This survey's respondents replied with an identical percentage (7.8%) for the two approaches listed above as motives for IR adoption.

The responses given about motivations for IR adoption in the research done in Indonesia before and this research are similar. In CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), most people (63%) have indicated that the most popular motivation method is to satisfy stakeholders and other stakeholders. As same as Sri Lanka, the next majority of respondents (49%) in Indonesia said that they were motivated to adopt IR after learning that their competitors or similar companies prepare integrated reports. Thus, it appears that the opinions about motivations for IR adoption are similar between the respondents in Indonesia and Sri Lanka.

Perceived Challenges of IR

The top three hurdles to implementing IR were recognized as preparation expenditures (60.1%), a lack of suitable information systems to create the IR (47.8%), and a fear of releasing market and/or price-sensitive information (39.9%). They believe that the advantages of IR outweigh the expenses, but the costs of creating integrated reports will rise. Other obstacles highlighted were a lack of connection and an integrated process (35.3%), as well as a lack of support from the Board of Directors and senior management (30.1%). The lack of instruction on how to develop an IR was cited by 28.8% of respondents. It indicates that organizations must undergo training and other educational activities in order to implement IR effectively. Furthermore, a sizable proportion of respondents (27.6%) stated that opposition from the grassroots level is another issue in IR. Similarly, 18.2%, 12.8%, and 3.1% of respondents claimed that inadequate proof of investor interest, fear of lawsuit, and other factors are barriers to IR adoption.

The following subject of discussion in the challenges of implementing IR is whether the firm will continue to create a separate sustainability report in addition to the integrated reports. In addition to IR, 49% of the 102 respondents plan to submit separate sustainability reports. Furthermore, 37.3% of respondents responded that they do not create separate sustainability reports in addition to IR. The remaining 13.7% expressed uncertainty.

Primary Recipients and Preparers of IR

In the present study, current investors (50%) and potential investors (18.6%) were identified as the primary recipients of IR. After that, most people (13.7%) indicated that the general public is the primary recipient of IR. The remainder identified customers (5.9%) and regulators (4.9%) as the primary recipients of IR, respectively. Similar percentages (2.9%) indicated that the primary recipients of IR were analysts and other recipients such as academics. The lowest percentage (1%) of IR's primary recipients are listed as suppliers. According to CASA FRANCA LOAYZA (2018), current investors and potential investors have responded to more people as the primary recipients of IR. This response is similar in Sri Lanka and Indonesia. Then analysts, regulators, the general public, customers, suppliers, and others are listed as primary recipients of IR respectively. The above response is completely different from the response given by Sri Lankan accounting experts.

Figure 1: Primary Recipients of IR

Source: Survey Data 2023

Most of the respondents said that top management is primarily responsible for preparing the integrated report. According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), they also said that top management is primarily responsible for the preparation of integrated reports. Here, the highest percentage of 50% of the respondents said that the board of directors is responsible for preparing integrated reports. Then it was found that CFO has 24.5% responsibility and CEO has 19.6% responsibility. As above, more than 50% of the respondents said that top management has the primary responsibility for preparing integrated reports. 4.9% of respondents said that sustainable practitioners have primary responsibility for preparing integrated reports. Likewise, the lowest percentage (1%) said that the responsibility lies with the auditors. None of the respondents said that there is an integrated reporting responsibility for public relations and others. According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), it was found that the primary responsibility for the preparation of integrated reports lies with the CEO, board of directors, and CFO respectively. It is similar to the findings of the Sri Lanka survey. But the rest said that public relations, sustainable practitioners, and auditors respectively have the primary responsibility of preparing integrated reports. These results are different from Sri Lanka's results.

Figure 2: Primary Preparers of IR

Source: Survey Data 2023

Next, the respondents were then asked to rank the significance of leadership in IR implementation on a five-point scale, with one being 'Not significant at all' and five being 'Very important'. The majority of respondents (40.2%) agreed that leadership plays an essential role in adopting IR. 36.3% believe that leadership has a key role in the implementation of IR. The remainder of the sample rated the role of leadership in the implementation of IR as neutral (12.7%), not at all significant (7.8%), and low importance (2.9%).

Finally, it was asked whether the stakeholders need to audit the IR to rely on the reports. The highest percentage (68.6%) responded that an IR audit is necessary to rely on reports. 22.5% responded that an IR audit is not necessary to rely on reports. A small group of 8.8% said that they had not sure about it. In CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), 57% answered 'Yes', 39 % answered 'Maybe' and 4% answered 'No'.

Standards and Implementation

When considering the form of IR implementation in Sri Lanka, the highest percentage of respondents (37.3%) said that it is market driven. Most of the rest (34.3%) said that it operates as regulatory-driven (explain or apply). A group of 28.4% said that the implementation of IR should be mandatory in Sri Lanka. According to CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018), the response to this query varies. That is, they defined IR implementation as mandatory (48%), regulatory-driven (explain or apply- 37%), and market-driven (15%) respectively. The chart below shows how IR should be implemented in Sri Lanka.

Figure 3: How should IR be implemented in Sri Lanka

Source: Survey Data 2023

More over two-thirds (76.5%) of respondents stated that broad implementation of IR in Sri Lanka would make it a more appealing environment to do business, while 14.7% were unsure and 8.8% disagreed. The current study's positive findings exceeded those of the CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018) survey (66%).

Finally, more than two-thirds (82.4%) agreed that the use of IR would be more attractive to Sri Lankan business investors. Of the rest, 11.8% were not sure about it and 5.9% disagreed with that statement. Here also, the positive findings in the current study were higher than those in the CASAFRANCA LOAYZA (2018) survey (61%).

Support, Promotion, and Training

The study's findings indicate a substantial preference for Integrated Reporting (IR) adoption in Sri Lanka. Respondents highlighted the importance of increased government, agency, and industry assistance in successfully implementing this method. Notably, respondents cited a suitable implementation timeframe (48%) and the availability of technical and preparatory guidance (19.6%) as key criteria. Additionally, respondents expressed a desire for some form of appreciation for adopting IR (18.6%) and financial incentives (13.7%) to facilitate adoption. These incentives could encompass financial rewards, tax deductions, and other inducements, potentially accelerating IR adoption among companies. These findings echo those of a previous survey by Casafranca Loayza (2018), which similarly emphasized the importance of a

reasonable implementation timeframe, financial incentives, technical guidance, and appreciation for IR adoption.

The responses given by the respondents to the activities that can be done to improve the knowledge of IR by the professional accounting bodies and promote this approach in Sri Lanka.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The exploration of Integrated Reporting (IR) perceptions within Sri Lankan companies reveals a notable familiarity with the concept among accounting experts, alongside a keen interest in further comprehension. However, despite recognition of its potential benefits, concerns persist regarding perceived challenges in IR adoption. Leadership commitment emerges as pivotal, with top management's role in driving IR implementation being underscored, highlighting the importance of organizational culture and leadership engagement. The motivations behind IR adoption vary, ranging from enhancing reporting quality to meeting stakeholder demands and gaining competitive advantages.

To foster broader IR adoption in Sri Lanka, several recommendations can be proposed. Firstly, professional accounting bodies should lead educational initiatives, including seminars and workshops, to enhance IR understanding among practitioners. Leadership engagement is critical, with top management encouraged to champion IR implementation within their organizations. Regulatory support, including technical assistance and financial incentives, can further incentivize companies to embrace IR. Collaboration among stakeholders, facilitated through platforms for knowledge sharing and best practice dissemination, is essential for promoting IR adoption. Continued research into IR's benefits, challenges, and best practices in the Sri Lankan context is imperative to identify effective strategies for overcoming adoption barriers.

Advancing IR adoption in Sri Lanka holds promise for enhancing corporate reporting quality, transparency, and stakeholder engagement. By implementing the recommended strategies, stakeholders can collectively create an enabling environment for IR adoption, contributing to the sustainable growth and development of the Sri Lankan business landscape.

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